

A Clinical Study of Endoscopic Dacryocystorhinostomy at a Tertiary Care Centre

Mahesh V Kattimani¹, Shweta Anand², Anuvind³

¹Associate Professor, Department of ENT, PMCH, Udaipur

²Associate Professor, Department of ENT, PMCH, Udaipur

³3rd Year Resident, PMCH, Udaipur

Received: 21-06-2024 / Revised: 04-07-2024 / Accepted: 20-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Shweta Anand

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Traditionally external skin incision was used for distal obstruction of nasolacrimal duct which was replaced by endoscopic dacryocystorhinostomy after the introduction of nasal endoscope.

Aim: To study advantages, complications and comorbidities of endoscopic dacryocystorhinostomy.

Materials and Methods: The study was done in fifty patients diagnosed with chronic dacryocystitis. This study included men, women and children of various age group who presented with chronic epiphora. Patency of nasolacrimal duct was checked by lacrimal sac syringing with normal saline at follow up visits at the end of first, second and third week.

Results: The maximum number of cases of chronic dacryocystitis belonged to the age group of 41-60 years. A female preponderance was noticed with 28 (56%) females. There were 2 cases (4%) with epistaxis, 3 cases (6%) with nasal synechiae and 8 cases (16%) with postoperative crusting. Rest of the patients had uneventful postoperative period. The patency of lacrimal passage was investigated by sac syringing with normal saline. All 50 (100%) cases were patent on lacrimal syringing at the end of the 1st and 2nd week and 47 (94%) at the end of 3rd week.

Conclusion: Endoscopic Dacryocystorhinostomy is a minimally invasive, safe procedure without major complication. It can be performed as a day care procedure with excellent results and is preferred by patients as it is cosmetically acceptable compared to external dacryocystorhinostomy.

Keywords: Chronic Dacryocystitis, Endoscopic Dacryocystorhinostomy, Nasolacrimal Duct.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Inflammation of the lacrimal sac is known as dacryocystitis which usually occurs because of nasolacrimal duct obstruction. The essential symptom is epiphora, aggravated by conditions such as exposure to wind, fumes etc. There may be a swelling at the site of the sac called mucocoele. On pressure over the sac, mucopus or pus regurgitates through the puncta, or more rarely passes down into the nose. [1]

Infants and females over 40 years of age are generally affected. Dacryocystitis can be of two types acute and chronic. Chronic dacryocystitis can be congenital or acquired. Congenital dacryocystitis is almost always chronic while acquired dacryocystitis may be acute or chronic.

Congenital blockage of the lacrimal drainage system usually occurs due to imperforate valve of Hasner which covers the end of the NLD, and it occurs in 2%–6% of newborn infants [2]

Nasal polypi, a hypertrophied inferior turbinate, or

extreme deviation of the septum may cause obstruction to the lower end of NLD leading to accumulation of secretions in the lacrimal sac which is easily infected. Untreated chronic dacryocystitis tends to progress and leading to an atonic lacrimal sac thus paving the way for formation of lacrimal abscess. [3]

The surgical modality of management of dacryocystitis is continuously evolving and has evolved considerably since its inception.

Chronic dacryocystitis due to nasolacrimal duct obstruction (post-saccal) was traditionally treated by External dacryocystorhinostomy. Toti in 1904 first described this operation. However, the intranasal approach for dacryocystorhinostomy was already described by Caldwell in 1863 via trephination of nasolacrimal duct. [4]

The increasing use of endoscopic techniques for performance of functional intranasal and sinus surgery has allowed the visualization of nasal cavity and has awakened interest in transnasal approach to

the nasolacrimal apparatus.

Endoscopic Dacryocystorhinostomy has the distinct advantages of no surface scar externally and does not damage the lacrimal pump mechanism which usually occurs in external dacryocystorhinostomy.⁵

Materials and Methods

The present study was carried out in fifty patients presenting with epiphora in the department of ENT, Pacific Medical College and Hospital, Udaipur during 8th December 2022 to 31st April 2024.

Inclusion Criteria: All patients presenting with epiphora with saccal or postsaccal obstruction.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients of Dacryocystitis where obstruction was at the level of punctal, canaliculi or common canaliculi.

Patients of acute dacryocystitis

Detailed ocular and systemic history were taken. Patients were examined with reference to the lacrimal apparatus. A detailed ocular examination was done by ophthalmologist. Rhinoscopy was done to look for any significant nasal pathology. The patency of the nasolacrimal duct was identified by lacrimal sac syringing with normal saline. Pre-anesthetic work up was done. All patients received a course of antibiotic starting one day prior to surgery and continued for 5 days. Follow up was performed post-surgery on the end of 1st week, 2nd

week and 3rd week.

Surgical Procedure

A 4mm 0^o nasal endoscope was used. The nasal cavity was topically decongested with a mixture of 10ml of xylocaine 4% + 5ml of adrenaline (1:10000). The mucosa of the lateral nasal wall infiltrated with 2ml of 2% Xylocaine with 1:1,00,000 adrenalin just anterior to the uncinat process.

The 1.5 x 2 cm posterior based mucosal flap was fashioned. Lacrimal bone and maxillary bone punched out to reveal the sac & confirmed endoscopically by pressure on the lacrimal sac from outside over the medial canthus. The mucosa of the sac was incised by a sickle knife leading to serous or mucopurulent liquid discharging out of the sac was noticed. Then with a special right angled true cut forceps or with Blakesely's forceps inferomedial wall of the sac was removed.

Then lacrimal sac syringing was done with diluted methylene blue dye from outside and free flow of the methylene blue was observed endoscopically.

Gel foam packing was done.

Postoperatively, all patients were given systemic antibiotic and analgesics for 5 days. All patients were followed at first, second and third week post-operatively to look for any complication.

Figure 1: Kerrisons bone punch used to expose lacrimal sac

Figure 2: Exposure of Lacrimal Sac

Figure 3: Incision given on the lacrimal sac

Results

Table 1 : Age Distribution

Age (in years)	No of Patients	Percentage (%)
1-20	4	8
21-40	14	28
41-60	24	48
61-80	6	12
81-100	2	4
Total	50	100

Figure 8: Age Distribution

Age Distribution

Most of the patients were in 41-60 years age group. The youngest being 9 years and the oldest was 91 years old and the mean age was 46.22 years. 24 (48%) cases belonged to the age group of 41-60

years. This was followed by 14 (28%) cases in the age group of 21-40 years and 6 (12%) cases in the age group of 61-80 years. This was followed by 4 cases (8.0%) in the age group of 1-20 years and 2 cases (4.0%) in the age group of 81-100 years.

Table 2 : Sex Distribution

Sex	No of patients	Percentage(%)
Male	22	44
Female	28	56
Total	50	100

Figure 9 : Sex Distribution

Sex distribution of the patients: Table 2 shows the sex distribution of the patients. There were 28 (56%) female patients and 22 (44%) male patients. Male: Female ratio 1:1.3

Table 3: Laterality of symptoms

Laterality	No of patients	Percentage(%)
Right	33	66
Left	15	30
B/L	2	4
Total	50	100

Figure 10 : Laterality Of Symptoms

Laterality of symptoms

Table 3 shows laterality of symptoms.

There were total 33 cases (66%) with right sided symptoms.

There were total 15 cases (30%) with left sided symptoms.

There were total 2 cases (4%) with bilateral symptoms

Table 4: Patients with DNS

DNS	No of patients	Percentage(%)
With DNS	8	16
Without DNS	42	84
Total	50	100

Figure 11 : Patients Wit DNS

Patients with DNS: Table 4 shows associated DNS which was seen in 8 patients (16%), rest of them had nor-

mal nasal anatomy

Table 5: Intraoperative Complication

Intraoperative Complication	No of patients	Percentage(%)
Nil	49	98
Bleeding	1	2
Total	50	100

Figure 12 : Intraoperative Complication

Table 5 shows intraoperative complications.

There was one case (2.0%) which was affected by intraoperative complication of nasal bleeding which was later on managed with nasal packing and bipolar cauterization.

Table 6: Postoperative complication

Postoperative complication	No of patients	Percentage(%)
Bleeding	2	4
Crusting	8	16
Synechae	3	6
Nil	37	74
Total	50	100

Figure 13 : Postoperative Complication

Postoperative complications

Table 6 shows postoperative complications:

There were 2 cases (4%) with epistaxis, 3 cases

(6%) with nasal synechiae and 8 cases (16%) with postoperative crusting.

Rest of the patients had uneventful postoperative period

Table 7: Patency at scheduled follow up

End of 1 st week		
End of 1 st week	No of patients	Percentage(%)
Patent	50	100
Blocked	0	0
Total	50	100

End of 2 nd week		
End of 2 nd week	No of patients	Percentage(%)
Patent	50	100
Blocked	0	0
Total	50	100

End of 3 rd week		
End of 3 rd week	No of patients	Percentage(%)
Patent	47	94
Blocked	3	6
Total	50	100

Patency At Scheduled Post Operative Follow Up:

Table 7 shows the patency rates at the scheduled follow up period.

The patency of lacrimal passage was investigated by sac syringing with normal saline. All 50 (100%) cases were patent on lacrimal syringing at the end of the 1st and 2nd week.

And 47 (94%) at the end of 3rd week.

Table 8: Outcome of surgery

Outcome	No of patients	Percentage(%)
Success	47	94
Failure	3	6
Total	50	100

Figure 14 : Outcome Of Surgery

Outcome Of Surgery at the end of 1 month
In 47(94%) patients the outcome was successful at

Discussion

In the present study most of the cases (48%)

the end of 1 months and in case of 3 (6%) patients it was unsuccessful.

belonged to the age group 41-60 years, youngest being 9 years and the oldest being 91 years. Out of fifty patients, 28(56%) patients were females and

22 (44%) were males.

Shay Keren et al in 2019 retrospectively analysed medical records of all consecutive patients who underwent DCR in 7 years (2010-2016) in which right side dacryocystitis was seen in 98 (53.5%) cases and left side dacryocystitis was seen in 85(46.5%) cases. In our study 33 (66%) patients had right side dacryocystitis, 15 (30%) patients had left side dacryocystitis and 2(4%) patients had B/L dacryocystitis.[6]

Junge Zhang et al in 2024 studied the prognosis of concurrent endoscopic dacryocystorhinostomy and nasal septoplasty for chronic dacryocystitis with moderate nasal septum deviation in 158 patients. They concluded that nasal septoplasty in cases with moderate septal deviation did not impact endoscopic DCR prognosis.[7]

Similarly in our study 8 patients (16%) had DNS and rest of the patients were free from DNS, But none of the 8 patients needed septoplasty as it was not obstructing the surgical field. This is in accordance with the study of Junge Zhang et al in 2024.

In our study we employed a posterior based mucosal flap with flap preservation which is in consonance with study done by Aneena Chacko et al in 2024.[8]

We did not encounter any cases of granuloma formation in follow up. This is in same perspective as in the study by Balaji Shankarrao Mane et al in 2023.[9]

D Deviprasad et al 2009[10] did endoscopic DCR in 24 patients out of which 9 (38%) of the 24 patients had complications. Three patients (12%) had intraoperative bleeding but complete hemostasis was achieved at the end of the procedure. One patient (4%) had ecchymosis and minimal cellulitis of the left lower eyelid which was successfully treated with antibiotics and anti-inflammatory medications. Two patients (8%) had granulation at the surgical site, which was removed during the follow-up endoscopic cleaning. One patient who had undergone concomitant FESS had a synechia between the middle turbinate and lateral wall, which had to be resected during the follow-up at 3rd week. Two nasolacrimal fistulae (8%) had partial stenosis at 3rd month follow-up. Endoscopic assessment with lacrimal syringing, showed partial block of the nasolacrimal fistula in 2 cases (08%) at 3 months.¹⁰ However in our study 14(28%) out of 50 patients had complications. 1 (2%) patient had intraoperative bleeding which was controlled during the procedure, postoperative bleeding was seen in 2 cases (4%), 3 cases (6%) with nasal synechia and 8 cases (16%) with postoperative crusting,

The patency of lacrimal passage was investigated

by sac syringing with normal saline. In our study fewer complication can be attributed to better operative equipment compared to 2009 article. All 50 (100%) cases were patent on lacrimal syringing at the end of the 1st, 2nd week and 47 (94%) at the end of 3rd week.

In our study we had 3 failure cases, All the cases were not having acute infection and none of the cases had fistula, hence there was no prior indication of silicon intubation. All the 3 cases subsequently underwent successful revision endoscopic DCR. The procedure was performed as a day care procedure with good results. As these cases presented with patent neo-ostium, the need of stent did not arise.

Conclusion

Endoscopic Dacryocystorhinostomy is a simple and safe procedure with a high success rate in experienced hands, is a minimally invasive procedure as it has direct approach to the sac. It is a surgery that can be performed as a day care procedure under local and general anesthesia with excellent results. It is cosmetically acceptable as it leaves no scars compared to external DCR which was done earlier, It also has the advantage of operating any intranasal pathology in the same sitting. It has a minimum risk of intraoperative and postoperative complications.

References

1. Parson's disease of the eye 23rd edition, chapter 24,pg 1100-1124
2. Nesi FA, Lishman RD, Levine MR. Ophthalmic Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery. 2nd ed. St. Louis: Mosby-Year Book, Inc; 1998
3. Sihota R, Ton R. Disease of the Lacrimal Apparatus Parson's Disease of Eye. 22nd ed. New Delhi: Elsevier; 2015. pp. 475-7.
4. Venkatachalam VP, Sanjay Agarwal. Endoscopic Dacryocystorhinostomy. Indian Journal of Otolaryngology Head and Neck Surg 2000; 52(4): 371-372.
5. Marcet MM, Kuk AK, Phelps PO. Evidence-based review of surgical practices in endoscopic endonasal dacryocystorhinostomy for primary acquired nasolacrimal duct obstruction and other new indications. Curr Opin Ophthalmol. 2014 Sep; 25(5):443-8.
6. Shay Keren, Abergel A, Manor A, Rosenblatt A, Koenigstein D, Leibovitch I, et al. Endoscopic dacryocystorhinostomy: reasons for failure. EYE. 2020;34(5):948-53.
7. Zhang J, Ming S, Qing H, Han W, Li S. Prognosis of concurrent endoscopic dacryocystorhinostomy and nasal septoplasty for chronic dacryocystitis with moderate nasal septum deviation. Indian J Ophthalmol. 2024 May 1; 7 2 (Suppl 3):S435-S440.
8. Chacko A, J K Y. Comparative Study of En-

- donasal Endoscopic Dacryocystorhinostomy with or without Preservation of Nasal Mucosal Flap. Indian J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg. 2024 Feb;76(1):894-898.
9. Mane BS, Naikwadi KB, Gavali RM. A Comparative Study Between Anterior-Posterior and Superior-Inferior Flap Suturing Technique in Endoscopic Dacryocystorhinostomy at our Tertiary Institution. Indian J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg. 2023 Dec;75(4):2927-2935.
10. Deviprasad D, Mahesh SG, Pujary K, Pillai S, Mallick SA, Jain V. Endonasal endoscopic dacryocystorhinostomy: our experience. Indian J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg. 2009 Sep; 61 (3):223-6.